

The impact of metallicity in the internal structure constants of low-mass, pre-main sequence stars

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Abstract

The internal structure constants, also known as apsidal motion constants (k_j , with $j=2, 3$ and 4), are important parameters in stellar astrophysics. They are mass concentration parameters and depend on the mass distribution throughout the star. We investigate how metallicity affects the k_j of low-mass, rotating, pre-main sequence (pre-MS) and main sequence (MS) stars in binary systems. With a version of the ATON stellar evolutionary code that takes into account the combined effects of tidal distortions (due to a companion star) and rotation on the equilibrium configuration of the stars, we generated for nine stellar masses (ranging $0.6-1.4 M_\odot$, in 0.25 steps), six sets of models with different metallicities ($-1.25 \leq [M/H] \leq 0.0$, in 0.25 steps). These models show that the k_j are virtually constant in the beginning of the pre-MS but they vary significantly with the stellar age during the later stages of this phase, specially for higher mass stars. During the MS, these constants increase with the metallicity for $M \leq 1.0 M_\odot$. For $M > 1.0 M_\odot$, the k_j values yielded by the models of lower metallicities become progressively higher as the stellar mass increases so that the k_j produced by the $[M/H] = -1.25$ models are higher than those produced by the $[M/H] = 0.00$ models for $1.4 M_\odot$. We test our results against observations by evaluating the impact of metallicity on the k_j used to calculate the apsidal motion rate of the double-lined eclipsing binary system EK Cep, whose secondary component is in the pre-MS. We conclude that erroneous assumptions on metallicities can have a significant impact on the determination of the k_j .

1 Introduction

The internal structure “constants”, also known as apsidal motion “constants”¹, are important parameters in stellar astrophysics. They are mass concentration parameters and depend on the mass distribution throughout the star, being essential to compute the theoretical apsidal motion rates in close binaries, and the comparison with observations constitutes an important test for evolutionary models. Landin *et al.* (2009) presented models for low-mass, pre-main sequence (pre-MS) stars that include the combined distortion effects of tidal and rotational forces on the equilibrium configuration of stars in order to investigate the interaction of both effects on the stellar structure and evolution. They analyzed the time evolution of the second order internal structure parameter (k_2) of a $1 M_\odot$ model obtained for four different chemical compositions. They found that metal-poorer stars evolve to more centrally condensed configurations than metal-richer ones. Landin *et al.* (2009) also compared their values of k_2 for $1 M_\odot$ standard models (without any distortion effect) at the ZAMS (zero-age main sequence) with those previously published in the literature (Hejlesen 1987, Claret & Gimenez 1989, 1992, Claret 2004, 2005). The values of k_2 obtained with standard models of Landin *et al.* (2009) were found to be smaller than those published by the authors mentioned above, and the k_2 calculated with distorted models were even smaller, independent of the chemical compositions.

In this work, we present new evolutionary models, includ-

ing calculations of internal structure parameters for six different chemical composition. We investigate how metallicity affects the internal structure parameters of low-mass, rotating pre-MS stars in binary systems and test our results against observations.

2 Models

The version of the ATON evolutionary code we use in this work (Landin *et al.*, 2006, 2009) is briefly described bellow. In our models, convection is treated according to the traditional Mixing Length Theory (Böhm-Vitense, 1958, with the convection efficiency parameter $\alpha=1.5$). Grey atmosphere models are used to obtain surface boundary conditions that matches the interior solution at optical depth $\tau = 2/3$. Here, we assume the solar chemical composition $X=0.7125$ and $Z=0.0175$ (taken from Anders & Grevesse, 1989, under the error bars) and that the elements are mixed instantaneously in convective regions. Our models were generated by considering rigid body rotation (Mendes *et al.*, 1999). The initial angular momentum of each model was obtained according to the Kawaler (1987) relation

$$J_{\text{kaw}} = 1.566 \times 10^{50} \left(\frac{M}{M_\odot} \right)^{0.985} \text{ g cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}. \quad (1)$$

In order to take into account the tidal distortion effect of a companion star, we considered that the secondary star is a point mass of the same mass as its primary. The binary separation is assumed to be 7 times the primary stellar radius (for more details, see Landin *et al.*, 2009).

¹These internal structure constants k_j vary significantly with age and metallicity for the same mass, as shown in Figure 1 for $j = 2$, but the same is true for $j=3$ and 4 . Therefore, we will refer to them as parameters.

Figure 1: Second order internal structure parameters (k_2) as a function of age t .

3 Results

We generated six sets of models ($0.6 \leq M \leq 1.4 M_\odot$, in $0.1 M_\odot$ steps) for different metallicities ($-1.25 \leq [M/H] \leq 0.0$, in 0.25 steps) by using a version of the ATON stellar evolutionary code that takes into account the combined effects of tidal distortions (due to a companion star) and rotation on the equilibrium configuration of the stars. With these models, we obtained new values of apsidal motion parameters (k_j , with $j=2, 3$ and 4). In Figure 1, we show $\log(k_2)$ as a function of age for all stellar models, as an example for all k_j s.

The general behavior of time evolution of k_j is similar for all j and the main difference between them is the strength (k_j decreases with increasing j for a given mass and age). The parameters k_j vary significantly with the stellar age during the later stages of the pre-MS, especially for higher mass stars. During the main sequence (MS), these parameters increase with the metallicity for $M < 1.0 M_\odot$. For $M > 1.0 M_\odot$, the k_j values yielded by the lower metallicity models become

progressively higher as the stellar mass increases, so that the k_j produced by the $[M/H] = -1.25$ models are higher than those produced by the $[M/H] = 0.00$ models for $1.3-1.4 M_\odot$.

The values of $\log(k_j)$ as a function of stellar mass and metallicity at the ZAMS (following the criterion of Iben 1965, shown as crosses (\times) for each mass and metallicity in Figure 1) are shown in Figure 2 for all sets of models. At the ZAMS, the internal structure parameters k_j decrease with the stellar mass for $[M/H] = 0$ and -0.25 models in the whole mass range analyzed. For metallicities smaller than -0.25 , this behavior persists up to a certain mass, which vary from model to model and is smaller for models with lower metallicities. This seems to be related to the radiative core formation, which occurs earlier for metal poorer stars.

We compared our 2nd order internal structure parameters with those published by Claret (2019) for $1 M_\odot$ and $[M/H] = 0.0, -0.5$ and -1.0 and found that our k_2 are, on average, 0.2 dex (in logarithm scale) smaller than his ones.

4 Comparisons with observations

Internal structure parameters are essential to compute the theoretical apsidal motion rate ($\dot{\omega}$) in close binaries. We test our theoretical results by evaluating the impact of metallicity on k_2 , which enters in the calculation of $\dot{\omega}$ of the 17 Myr, double-lined eclipsing binary system EK Cep (anomalous orbital and apsidal motion periods $P=4^d428$ and $U=4500$ yrs, respectively, Claret 2006), whose secondary component is in the pre-MS. The fundamental parameters of that system are in Table 1.

Table 1: Absolute dimensions of EK Cep (Claret, 2006).

Component	Primary	Secondary
Mass (M_{\odot})	2.029 ± 0.023	1.124 ± 0.012
Radius (R_{\odot})	1.579 ± 0.007	1.315 ± 0.006
$\log(g/\text{cm s}^{-2})$	3.349 ± 0.010	4.251 ± 0.006
$\log(L/L_{\odot})$	1.17 ± 0.04	0.19 ± 0.07
$\log(T_{\text{eff}}/\text{K})$	3.954 ± 0.010	3.756 ± 0.015

As the apsidal motion rate is proportional to the 2nd order internal structure parameter, which decrease with the metallicity, the theoretical value of $\dot{\omega}$ can be considerably affected by erroneous assumptions about metallicity (see Table 2).

Table 2: Apsidal motion related quantities for EK Cep.

Quantity	[M/H]=0.0	Observed	[M/H]=-1.0
$\log(k_2)$	-2.21 ± 0.07	-2.09 ± 0.09	-2.31 ± 0.01
U(yrs)	5200 ± 400	4500 ± 700	5700 ± 100
$\dot{\omega}$ ($10^{-3} \text{ } ^\circ/\text{cycle}$)	0.85 ± 0.07	0.97 ± 0.15	1.090 ± 0.007

5 Conclusions

The values of k_j vary significantly throughout the stellar evolution, showing a decreasing trend during the pre-MS but in such a manner that, for $M < 1 M_{\odot}$, higher metallicities result in higher k_j values, while for $M > 1 M_{\odot}$ stars with lower metallicities revert this trend as they approach the ZAMS. Our k_2 values for $1 M_{\odot}$ and [M/H]= 0.0, -0.5 and -1.00 are smaller than those of Claret (2019). Mistaken metallicity assumptions can affect apsidal motion rates determinations.

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References

- Anders, E. & Grevesse, N. 1989, *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta*, 53, 197.
 Böhm-Vitense, E. 1958, *ZA*, 46, 108.
 Claret, A. 2004, *A&A*, 424, 919.
 Claret, A. 2005, *A&A*, 440, 647.
 Claret, A. 2006, *A&A*, 445, 1061.
 Claret, A. 2019, *A&A*, 628, A29.
 Claret, A. & Gimenez, A. 1989, *A&AS*, 81, 1.
 Claret, A. & Gimenez, A. 1992, *A&AS*, 96, 255.
 Hejlesen, P. M. 1987, *A&AS*, 69, 251.
 Iben, I. 1965, *ApJ*, 141, 993.
 Kawaler, S. D. 1987, *PASP*, 99, 1322.
 Landin, N. R., Mendes, L. T. S., & Vaz, L. P. R. 2009, *A&A*, 494, 209.
 Landin, N. R., Ventura, P., D'Antona, F., Mendes, L. T. S., & Vaz, L. P. R. 2006, *A&A*, 456, 269.
 Mendes, L. T. S., D'Antona, F., & Mazzitelli, I. 1999, *A&A*, 341, 174.

Figure 2: Internal structure parameters (k_j) as a function of mass at the ZAMS.